

REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder Dominates Heterogeneity in Longitudinal Analysis of Parkinson's Disease

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Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD) exhibits significant clinical heterogeneity, yet the longitudinal interplay between multidomain symptoms and structural biomarkers remains under-explored. We analyzed 5-year data from the PPMI cohort (N=855) using multivariate latent class mixed modeling (multlcmm) to identify distinct progression phenotypes. A two-step externVar approach assessed class predictors, while Linear Mixed Models and XGBoost characterized longitudinal atrophy and early-stage subtype prediction. Three classes emerged: Stable High-Burden (Class 1, n=173), Low-Burden (Class 2, n=568), and Increasing-Burden (Class 3, n=114). Model assignment was primarily driven by RBDSQ trajectories (ARI = 0.96) and validated by significantly lower baseline UPSIT scores in Classes 1 and 3 ($p < .01$). Class 1 exhibited pronounced baseline atrophy, whereas Class 3 demonstrated accelerated longitudinal structural change. SHAP analysis identified baseline RBDSQ as the most critical predictor of class membership.

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Source Repository

 [impact-scholars/2026-longitudinal-subtyping-ppmi](https://github.com/impact-scholars/2026-longitudinal-subtyping-ppmi)

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Data Availability

Published via Impact Scholars; original development repository.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Translational research mandates from the National Institutes of Health emphasize the urgent need to characterize the natural history of Parkinson's disease (PD) and develop objective stratification tools (Sieber *et al.*, 2014). Large-scale cohort studies, such as the Parkinson's Precision Medicine Initiative (PPMI), now provide the infrastructure to discover data-driven progression subtypes and accelerate targeted therapeutic trials (Marek *et al.*, 2018). Historically, stratification relied on baseline motor features such as tremor-dominant and PIGD phenotypes (Jankovic *et al.*, 1990). However, both clinical and data-driven subtypes are predominantly early-stage phenomena, often coalescing into a more uniform clinical presentation as the disease advances (Sauerbier *et al.*, 2016).

Comprehensive multidomain clustering studies have significantly advanced our understanding of PD heterogeneity. By defining phenotypic profiles at a static baseline, standard distance-based clustering approaches have successfully identified subgroups with distinctly divergent clinical outcomes, such as the fast-progressing "diffuse malignant" phenotype (Fereshtehnejad *et al.*, 2015; 2017; Velucci *et al.*, 2025). Notably, this same temporal approach is frequently mirrored even in studies utilizing advanced machine learning frameworks (Markello *et al.*, 2021): phenotypic classes are established cross-sectionally, and longitudinal follow-up is only used post hoc to observe the progression of these fixed groups. Conversely, approaches that explicitly subtype patients based on progression rates have demonstrated the immense prognostic value of temporal data (Faghri *et al.*, 2018). Yet, these machine learning methods often compress longitudinal follow-up into static summary vectors, obscuring the dynamic shape of the disease course.

To capture actual symptom evolution, univariate latent class models have mapped individual domains over time, such as cognition (Pourzinal *et al.*, 2024), autonomic function (Chen *et al.*, 2021), and motor severity (He *et al.*, 2023). Evaluating these axes in isolation limits our understanding of PD as a multi-system disorder. To bridge this gap, our research undertakes an exploratory investigation using a multivariate longitudinal Latent Class Mixed Model (LCMM). Rather than assuming equal contribution across all symptom domains, this multi-dimensional approach allows the natural variance of the cohort to dictate the clustering, revealing which clinical scales predominantly drive longitudinal heterogeneity.

Finally, we relate these emergent clinical phenotypes to targeted biological metrics. Specifically, further relate these phenotypes to structural MRI, as atrophy patterns track both clinical severity and trans-neuronal spread of PD pathology (Zeighami *et al.*, 2015). As highlighted in a recent review (Filidei *et al.*, 2025), bridging data-driven subtypes and biological correlates is a critical priority to ensure clinical classifications reflect true pathophysiological differences

2. RESULTS

Figure 1: Observed mean trajectories of the four class indicator variables defining the

multicmm model. Class 1 = stable high-burden, Class 2 = stable low-burden, Class 3 = increasing-burden.

E: Heatmap of LMM-derived annual change rates for the 20 selected MRI regions. Colors indicate standardized effect sizes (z-statistics); asterisks denote nominally significant differences (unadjusted).

F: Class-specific SHAP feature importance profiles. Bars show mean absolute SHAP values, reflecting the global contribution of baseline features to XGBoost class assignment.

2.a. Latent Class Identification and Trajectories

Multivariate LCMM identified a three-class solution as optimal based on the lowest BIC, mean posterior probabilities, class size, and relative entropy criteria (Table 1), see Supp.Methodology for details : a Stable High-Burden class (Class 1, n = 173, 20.2%), a Low-Burden class (Class 2, n = 568, 66.4%), and an Increasing-Burden class (Class 3, n = 114, 13.3%). Observed mean trajectories are shown in Figure 1 (A–D). Class 1 started with the highest REM Sleep Behavior Disorder Screening Questionnaire (RBDSQ) scores, which showed a slight decline by Year 5. Class 2 remained consistently below the cutoff throughout follow-up. Class 3 crossed the cutoff around Year 2 and reached levels comparable to Class 1 by Year 5. For orthostatic systolic blood pressure drop (Δ SBP), Classes 1 and 3 showed increases in later years, while Class 2 remained low. Movement Disorder Society–Unified Parkinson’s Disease Rating Scale Part III (UPDRS Part III) scores increased in all classes, with the steepest rise observed in Class 1. Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) scores declined over time in Classes 1 and 3, whereas Class 2 remained stable. RBDSQ accounted for the largest variance proportion (39.1%), substantially exceeding Δ SBP (0.74%), MoCA (0.50%), and UPDRS-III (0.20%); the multivariate class structure showed strong agreement with the RBDSQ-only solution (ARI = 0.96; Cramér’s V = 0.95) (Table S1; Table S2). Baseline characteristics are described in Supp.Baseline.

K	Log-likelihood	Relative entropy	AIC	BIC	Proportion per class (%)	Average posterior probability	OCC
1	-18471.82	1.00	36969.64	37031.40	100.00		
2	-18368.28	0.79	36768.56	36844.58	28.77 71.23	0.89 0.96	
3	-18297.93	0.75	36633.87	36724.14	20.23 66.43 13.33	0.87 0.92 0.79	26.00 5.98 24.00
4	-18387.10	0.27	36818.20	36922.73	33.80 0.35 34.15 31.70	0.76 0.35 0.35 0.34	

Table 1: Multivariate LCMM model (z-score) selection and classification metrics

2.b. Baseline Neuroimaging and Biomarker Associations

Baseline MRI ORs are reported per standard deviation increase to facilitate interpretation, as eTIV-normalized volumes are measured on very small scales. Clinical and biofluid markers remained on their raw scales.

Baseline olfactory function (UPSIT) was significantly lower in both the high-burden ($p = 0.005$) and increasing-burden ($p = 0.002$) classes (Table 2), validating the model’s capacity to capture external clinical heterogeneity. Subcortical profiles further differentiated the cohorts: smaller baseline volumes of the thalamus ($p = 0.026$) and putamen ($p = 0.023$) predicted high-burden class membership, whereas a larger baseline pallidum volume ($p = 0.033$) predicted increasing-burden membership.

2.c. Longitudinal Structural Change

Longitudinal Linear Mixed Models revealed divergent temporal dynamics between classes (Table 3). The high-burden class showed unadjusted trends of accelerated atrophy across five regions: the amygdala, inferior temporal gyrus, parahippocampal gyrus, superior parietal lobule, and caudal middle frontal gyrus. Conversely, the increasing-burden class exhibited four unadjusted longitudinal trends: slower caudate atrophy alongside accelerated ventricular and choroid plexus expansion.

No regional structural slopes survived False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction across the 20 evaluated regions. Consequently, these longitudinal variations represent exploratory trends rather than definitive trajectory markers.

Predictor	N	Odds Ratio (Class 1)	p-value (Class 1)	Odds Ratio (Class 3)	p-value (Class 3)
Sex (Male=1)	855	3.278	<.001	1.633	0.093
Education (Years)	855	0.975	0.471	0.984	0.718
Age	855	1.011	0.432	1.005	0.775
Striatal SBR Caudate (full)	846	0.436	0.075	0.550	0.323
Striatal SBR Putamen (full)	846	0.767	0.579	0.249	0.054
UPSIT (full)	834	0.963	0.005	0.948	0.002
CSF-SAA (Positive=1) (full)	796	1.535	0.208	5.983	0.109
CSF α -synuclein	240	0.999	0.130	1.000	0.490
CSF phosphorylated- τ	240	1.117	0.203	1.062	0.345
CSF amyloid- β	240	0.999	0.630	0.999	0.248
UPSIT (overlap)	240	0.966	0.233	0.954	0.076
Serum NfL Chain	240	1.043	0.167	0.978	0.560
Striatal SBR Caudate (overlap)	240	0.375	0.425	1.089	0.941
Striatal SBR Putamen (overlap)	240	0.163	0.222	0.098	0.092
APOE ϵ 4 (Carrier=1)	240	0.911	0.875	0.744	0.575
Thalamus	474	0.596	0.026	0.868	0.527
Putamen	474	0.613	0.023	0.899	0.630
Caudate	474	1.348	0.133	0.845	0.393
Pallidum	474	1.147	0.478	1.511	0.033
Insula	474	1.361	0.196	0.911	0.654
Amygdala	474	1.000	0.974	0.924	0.732
Hippocampus	474	1.537	0.058	1.036	0.903

Inferior Temporal	474	0.954	0.807	1.057	0.776
Para-Hippocampal	474	0.737	0.090	1.015	0.933
Posterior Cingulate	474	1.048	0.825	0.863	0.494
Superior Parietal	474	1.150	0.507	0.903	0.669
Middle Frontal	474	0.863	0.386	1.024	0.903
Anterior Cingulate	474	1.443	0.135	1.215	0.404

Table 2: Multinomial Logistic Regression on Baseline Biomarkers (Reference: Class 2). **Bolded** values indicate $p < 0.05$. ORs for MRI-derived features are standardized, other ORs are given in terms of raw units. Age and Sex were included as controls in all regressions, Education was additionally controlled for in all regressions except for the one carried out on the MRI-derived features.

Region	p-value (Class 1)	FDR $q < 0.10$ (Class 1)	p-value (Class 3)	FDR $q < 0.10$ (Class 3)
Thalamus	0.950	0.990	0.835	0.879
Caudate	0.684	0.808	0.036	0.204
Putamen	0.433	0.618	0.306	0.680
Hippocampus	0.561	0.748	0.090	0.258
Choroid Plexus	0.990	0.990	0.044	0.204
Pallidum	0.271	0.542	0.990	0.990
Lateral Ventricle	0.393	0.618	0.020	0.202
Inf. Lat. Ventricle	0.054	0.180	0.009	0.177
Cerebral White Matter	0.799	0.888	0.430	0.782
WM Hypointensities	0.067	0.192	0.378	0.756
Amygdala	0.010	0.120	0.768	0.853
Insula	0.414	0.618	0.757	0.853
Inferior Temporal	0.012	0.120	0.470	0.783
Para-Hippocampal	0.028	0.180	0.651	0.853
Posterior Cingulate	0.148	0.330	0.069	0.231
Superior Parietal	0.047	0.180	0.145	0.363
Rostral Middle Frontal	0.686	0.808	0.701	0.853
Caudal Middle Frontal	0.049	0.180	0.512	0.788
Rostral Anterior Cingulate	0.340	0.618	0.751	0.853
Caudal Anterior Cingulate	0.116	0.291	0.051	0.204

Table 3: Linear Mixed Models on MRI Volume and Cortical Thickness Trajectories (Reference: Class 2). P-values are shown for the differences in atrophy/expansion between classes. Unadjusted $p < 0.05$ results are indicated in **bold**. None of the results survived FDR correction. Age and sex were controlled for in all models.

2.d. Early-Stage Subtype Prediction

The XGBoost model achieved an AUC of 0.88 and cross-validated balanced accuracy of 0.73. Baseline RBDSQ was the single most discriminative predictor of class membership by both split frequency and information gain, tripling the next-ranked feature. Class-specific SHAP analysis (Figure 1 (F)) revealed that Class 1 was overwhelmingly driven by RBD severity; Class 2 showed a more distributed profile led by RBD, olfactory function, autonomic dysfunction, and anxiety; and Class 3 had the broadest SHAP profile with postural instability and dopaminergic imaging as notable contributors, consistent with its lower classification accuracy (F1 = 0.36). CSF α -synuclein SAA ranked prominently in native tree metrics but not in SHAP values, reflecting population-level rather than patient-level discriminative utility.

3. DISCUSSION

While RBD is a well-established prognostic marker, it is typically deployed as a static or binary baseline feature (Liu et al., 2021; Velucci et al., 2025). Our findings highlight its dynamic evolution: longitudinal RBDSQ trajectories contributed the majority of variance, driving the latent class structure and demonstrating that RBD-related heterogeneity persists well beyond the prodromal stage.

This longitudinal approach yields markedly different prognostic insights compared to baseline clustering. For instance, the highly cited diffuse/malignant phenotype (Fereshtehnejad et al., 2015) couples a wide breadth of severe baseline symptoms with rapid global progression. While our Class 1 shares this severe baseline multi-domain profile (Supp.Baseline) and resembles the RBD+ cluster (Velucci et al., 2025), its symptom progression was not exclusively the most rapid. Instead, Class 3 demonstrated the steepest multi-domain deterioration despite much milder baseline symptoms. Because our multivariate LCMM models domain-specific trajectories rather than collapsing metrics into a single composite score, these results suggest that initial symptom burden and progression rate represent distinct, decoupled dimensions of PD heterogeneity.

Our trajectory-derived subtypes align more closely with longitudinal RBD progression studies than with traditional baseline clustering. Our data-driven classes mirror the a priori groups defined by Ye et al. (2022). Their largest group, the non-RBD-stable phenotype, matches our low-burden stable class (Class 2). Our Class 3 strongly aligns with their “late-RBD” group (12.1% of their cohort), showing a late-emerging probable RBD trajectory that crosses the clinical threshold around Year 2. This transitional, high-risk phenotype exhibits baseline olfactory impairment and orthostatic hypotension (Y. Saitoh et al., 2018). Our high-burden Class 1 likely represents a combination of their pRBD-stable and pRBD-reversion phenotypes—supported by a slight reversion in Class 1’s RBDSQ during Years 4 and 5.

Smaller baseline thalamus and putamen volumes predicted high-burden class membership, consistent with their identification as early structural markers for pRBD and aggressive PD (Boucetta et al., 2016; Ellmore et al., 2010; Rahayel et al., 2019; Salsone et al., 2014). Conversely, increasing-burden membership predicted larger baseline pallidal volumes. Although pallidal atrophy has been linked to RBD progression, evidence for baseline pallidal differences is limited. Prior morphometric analyses show that PD patients without RBD exhibit localized pallidal surface contraction (Rahayel et al., 2019), which may contribute to apparent volumetric differences given our low-burden reference group.

Although longitudinal structural alterations did not survive strict FDR correction, their unadjusted trends offer exploratory mechanistic insights. The high-burden class exhibited accelerated atrophy in the amygdala, parahippocampal gyrus, and superior parietal lobule. Amygdalar atrophy directly aligns

with longitudinal pRBD findings (Yoon & Monchi, 2021) and contextualizes this cohort's significantly elevated baseline depression and anxiety (GDS/STAI). Furthermore, parahippocampal and superior parietal thinning mirror longitudinal structural progression patterns distinguishing RBD from non-RBD PD phenotypes (Ye *et al.*, 2022). Conversely, the increasing-burden class trended toward accelerated ventricular and choroid plexus expansion—radiological markers of central pan-atrophy and altered CSF dynamics linked to impaired glymphatic clearance (He *et al.*, 2023).

Finally, while we did not directly measure α -synuclein pathology, these distinct trajectories tentatively align with proposed models of Lewy body spatial progression. Class 1's early concurrent triad of RBD, autonomic, and olfactory dysfunction resembles a “body-first” or brainstem-early trajectory (Borghammer & Van Den Berge, 2019; Mastenbroek *et al.*, 2024). Conversely, Class 3's post-motor RBD onset and rapid cognitive decline suggests a “brain-first” origin with delayed, steep brainstem involvement. Class 2, persistently lacking RBD, may represent a phenotype where pathology remains temporarily confined to olfactory regions. Ultimately, the longitudinal timing of RBD expression appears to carry critical, albeit interpretive, pathophysiological weight.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

List of Abbreviations

AIC: Akaike Information Criterion
APOE: Apolipoprotein E (gene)
ARI: Adjusted Rand Index
AUC: Area Under the Curve
BIC: Bayesian Information Criterion
CSF: Cerebrospinal Fluid
CV: Cross-Validation
DAT: Dopamine Transporter (imaging)
eTIV: estimated Total Intracranial Volume
Hb: Hemoglobin
LCMM: Latent Class Mixed Model (R function)
LEDD: Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose
LMM: Linear Mixed Model
MCAR: Missing Completely at Random (statistical test)
MDS-UPDRS: Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale
MoCA: Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MRIQC: MRI Quality Control (pipeline)
OCC: Odds of Correct Classification
OR: Odds Ratio
PATNO: Patient Number (in PPMI)
PIGD: Postural Instability and Gait Difficulty
PD: Parkinson's Disease
PPMI: Parkinson's Precision Medicine Initiative
RBD: REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder
RBDSQ: REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder Screening Questionnaire
ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic
SAA: Seed Amplification Assay
SBP: Systolic Blood Pressure
SBR: Striatal Binding Ratio
SCOPA-AUT: Scales for Outcomes in Parkinson's Disease - Autonomic Dysfunction
SHAP: SHapley Additive exPlanations
STAI: State-Trait Anxiety Inventory
UPSIT: University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test
VIF: Variance Inflation Factor
WM: White Matter

Methodology

Participants:

Data acquired from Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) dataset (<https://www.ppmi-info.org/>), on 21 March 2026. PPMI is a multi-center, longitudinal, and observational study that was launched in 2010. Each PPMI site was approved by the appropriate institutional review board before study initiation, and they all fully adhere to the principles set forth in the Declaration of Helsinki. All subjects provided written informed consent prior participation.

Participants were included if they met the following criteria at baseline: (1) drug-naïve with a levodopa equivalent daily dose (LEDD) of 0; (2) disease duration within 2 years; (3) early-stage disease defined by

Hoehn-Yahr stage < 3; (4) no dementia; and (5) age onset \geq 50 years to exclude early-onset Parkinson's disease. Participants were followed for up to 5 years, and only those with two or more follow-up visits were included, resulting in a total of 855 participants with Parkinson's disease.

Trajectory analysis:

Analyses were performed in R (v4.5.3) and Python (v3.12.13). `multlcmm` function in the R package `lcmm` (Proust-Lima et al., 2017) was applied for trajectory analysis. This approach follows the rationale of group-based trajectory modeling (Nagin & Odgers, 2010), allowing several longitudinal markers measured on different clinical scales, to inform a common underlying latent disease process while accounting for marker-specific measurement relationships. Latent classes and individual membership probabilities were estimated within a maximum-likelihood framework, providing asymptotically unbiased parameter estimates under a missing-at-random (MAR) assumption. Follow-up time since baseline, measured in years, was used as the time indicator. The following steps were performed to optimize the analysis:

1. **Literature-informed scale selection:** Candidate scales were chosen to represent major PD progression domains based on prior subtyping studies. The initial set included RBDSQ, SCOPA-AUT, STAI, age- and education-adjusted SDMT T-scores, and the MDS-UPDRS Part III OFF-medication score (UPDRS Part III) (He et al., 2023; Velucci et al., 2025). However, modeling above five scales together failed to meet minimum criteria: mean posterior probabilities > 0.7 or minimum class proportions > 5%.
2. **Indicator refinement:** To ensure model construction from scales with longitudinal signals and optimal class separation, we evaluated candidate scales in univariate LCMM, and prioritized scales that had been studied in univariate model. The final set is RBDSQ, MoCA (Wang et al., 2025), UPDRS Part III, Δ SBP (Chen et al., 2021).
3. **Link function & distributional consideration:** Although nonlinear link functions better accommodate ceiling/floor effects and curvilinearity of psychometric scales (Proust-Lima et al., 2011), their application in our multivariate framework resulted in reduced classification quality (relative entropy < 0.7 or OCC < 5). Therefore, a linear link function was adopted for all indicators. To address MoCA's known curvilinearity and ceiling effect, square root transformation was applied prior to modeling (Wang et al., 2025).
4. **Random effects specification:** Models with random intercept-slope and random intercept only were both evaluated. Both identified a 3-class solution as optimal under linear link; however, the random intercept-slope model did not converge. The final model therefore specified random intercept only, with fixed and mixture components including both intercept and slope terms.
5. **Model selection:** Models with 1 to 4 classes were fitted. The final model was selected based on lowest BIC, mean posterior probabilities > 70%, minimum class size > 5%, and relative entropy > 0.7 (Lennon et al., 2018).
6. **Scale contribution assessment:** Residual standard error and variance explained proportion were examined to evaluate each indicator's contribution to the multivariate model.
7. **Class assignment validation:** To assess the consistency of class solutions, comparisons were performed using confusion matrices, Adjusted Rand Index (ARI), and Cramér's V.
8. **Sensitivity analyses:** Models were initially estimated using raw/pre-transformed scores. As z-standardized scores yielded identical class solutions (ARI = 1, Cramér's V = 1) while facilitating convergence in downstream analyses, z-standardized scores were adopted as the primary model specification.

Missingness and attrition:

The missing rates for RBDSQ, MoCA, Δ SBP, and UPDRS Part III were 0.88%, 1.09%, 2.99%, and 15.99%, respectively. LCMM accommodates incomplete longitudinal data, so no additional missingness handling was performed. Little's MCAR test was significant ($\chi^2 = 208$, $df = 28$, $p < .001$), indicating that data were not missing completely at random. Differential attrition was observed across classes, with Year 5 completion rates of 20.2%, 28.5%, and 41.2% for Classes 1, 2, and 3, respectively. As Class 1 also exhibited the overall highest baseline disease burden, attrition was likely associated with observed disease severity, supporting MAR as a reasonable assumption. Although LCMM is expected to limit the impact of differential attrition under MAR, later trajectory estimates for Class 1 are based on a smaller and potentially less severely affected subsample, which may limit their representativeness.

Clinical assessments:

The above selected four input clinical scales, each representing a core clinical domain (sleep, cognitive, autonomic, and motor):

1. **REM sleep behavior disorder (RBD):** Defined by a score ≥ 5 on the REM Sleep Behavior Disorder Screening Questionnaire (RBDSQ), a 10-item self-report instrument (maximum total score 13 points) designed to screen for RBD (Stiasny-Kolster et al., 2007).
2. **Global cognitive function:** Assessed through the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), adjusted for education. A score below 26 was used as the cutoff for cognitive impairment (Nasreddine et al., 2005).
3. **Orthostatic hypotension:** Quantified as the orthostatic change in systolic blood pressure (Δ SBP, supine SBP minus standing SBP upon standing). A Δ SBP ≥ 20 mmHg within 3 min of standing was considered indicative of clinically significant orthostatic hypotension (Freeman et al., 2011).
4. **Motor severity:** Evaluated using the Movement Disorder Society – Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS) Part III. A score between 33 to 58 was considered moderate motor impairment (Martínez-Martín et al., 2015).

MRI processing:

Baseline morphological and quality control data were obtained directly from the PPMI repository, derived from the FreeSurfer (v7.3.2) and MRIQC (v23.1.0) pipelines within the nipoppy framework (Bhagwat et al., 2023). To extend this to a longitudinal framework while maintaining computational efficiency, we independently processed all participants with available structural MRI at two or more visits ($n = 382$ of the total $N = 855$ inclusion cohort) using FastSurfer (v2.4.2) (Henschel et al., 2020). A total of 1036 scans were segmented, with volume statistics collated for regions defined by the Desikan-Killiany Atlas (Desikan et al., 2006). One participant was subsequently excluded due to technical issues involving missing entries and extreme hemispheric asymmetry. The specific processing parameters and code for this pipeline are documented in the Colab notebooks within our GitHub repository.

Quality control for the FreeSurfer data involved a rigorous outlier detection process using the Gap Statistic algorithm (Tibshirani et al., 2001) via the GapStatistics Python package (Loehr & Musab, 2025). We focused on three key MRIQC metrics: the coefficient of joint variation (CJV), contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR), and entropy focus criterion.

Secondary Analysis:

Relating latent class models to external variables requires careful handling of estimation bias. The traditional “one-step” method where covariates and the latent class model are estimated simultaneously often suffers from model instability, as the inclusion of predictors can shift the latent structure itself. To avoid this, many studies fall into the trap of the “naive” three-step method (assigning participants to classes before regression), which produces biased parameter estimates by ignoring classification uncertainty. We instead employed the improved three-step and two-step frameworks developed to account for this uncertainty (Bakk & Kuha, 2018; Bolck *et al.*, 2004; Nylund-Gibson & Masyn, 2016; Vermunt, 2010). Specifically, we utilized the `externVar` function in the `lcmm` package (Proust-Lima *et al.*, n.d.), opting for the two-step method over the three-step bootstrap to maintain computational efficiency while achieving comparable bias reduction.

Because the two-step regression function explicitly accounts for latent class assignment uncertainty, the variance-covariance estimation is highly parameter-heavy. Attempting to fit all covariates into a single unified model led to non-convergence (the algorithm destabilized with >15 predictors) and would have caused severe sample attrition due to varying missingness profiles across modalities. Consequently, we implemented a tiered modelling strategy. Non-MRI variables (curated clinical scales, fluid biomarkers, and DAT imaging) were evaluated in a complete-case overlap cohort (N = 240). Due to extreme data sparsity causing quasi-complete separation, the categorical SAA variable was restricted to an independent available-case sensitivity model (N = 796) to prevent sparse data bias from corrupting concurrent covariates, as this effect has been noted to potentially be more detrimental than missing variable bias (Greenland *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, SAA was binarized into “LBD-like” and “other” (combining MSA-like, inconclusive, and negative results), as these alternate categories were too sparse to be modelled independently even within the larger available-case cohort. MRI modalities were evaluated in a dedicated, parallel structural regression model (N = 474).

For the cross-sectional multinomial logistic regression, we utilized a mix of volume and thickness metrics derived from FreeSurfer, depending on the specific region. Subcortical volumes were normalized by estimated Total Intracranial Volume (eTIV) to account for head size (Voevodskaya *et al.*, 2014), while cortical thicknesses were normalized by mean cortical thickness. For the longitudinal Linear Mixed Models (LMM) investigating atrophy and ventricular expansion rates, we utilized FastSurfer outputs. Because FastSurfer does not provide an eTIV estimate, these volumes were instead normalized using `MaskVol`; this shift was a necessary adaptation to the respective software pipelines rather than a change in statistical strategy. Notably, FastSurfer segmentation directly provides volumes for cortical regions, allowing us to include them in the longitudinal analysis without the need to run time-intensive surface reconstructions across multiple timepoints.

Given the strict parameter limits of the uncertainty-adjusted regression, structural predictor selection required targeted refinement. Because our derived latent classes were predominantly characterized by their evolving REM sleep behaviour disorder (RBD) phenotypes, we restricted a priori region of interest (ROI) selection to 13 specific cortical and subcortical structures demonstrated in the literature to differ morphologically between PD patients with and without RBD (Boucetta *et al.*, 2016; Ellmore *et al.*, 2010; Lim *et al.*, 2016; Rahayel *et al.*, 2019; Salzone *et al.*, 2014; Ye *et al.*, 2022; Yoon & Monchi, 2021). Comparisons to healthy controls were omitted from this rationale as our models exclusively evaluated intra-disease phenotypic progression. To prevent multicollinearity in the regression, left and right hemisphere outputs

were averaged across all regions. Additionally, we consolidated the caudal and rostral sub-regions of the anterior cingulate and middle frontal cortices by summing their volumes, as the broader neuroimaging literature rarely distinguishes between these specific Desikan-Killiany parcellation subdivisions. Multicollinearity among the final selected predictors was assessed using Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) via the car library (John Fox & Sanford Weisberg, 2019), with all predictors yielding acceptable values (VIF < 5).

For the fluid biomarkers, red blood cells represent a significant source of interference in α -synuclein assays (Barbour et al., 2008). To account for this, we leveraged the PPMI hemoglobin (Hb) threshold indicators. Comparative analysis confirmed that α -synuclein levels did not differ significantly in median (Mann-Whitney U, $p = 0.627$) or distribution (Kolmogorov-Smirnov, $p = 0.495$) between samples with detectable Hb ($n = 60$) and those without ($n = 265$); consequently, the full sample was retained to maximize statistical power. Associations between monogenic PD variants and class membership were not evaluated due to the high prevalence of sporadic cases ($N = 808$, 94.5%). Similarly, APOE $\epsilon 4$ status was binarized (carrier vs. non-carrier) because homozygous cases were too infrequent for independent analysis.

The relationship between class membership and longitudinal atrophy was implemented using the hlme function via LMM. We acknowledge that this longitudinal analysis utilized a modal (naive) class assignment, as a corrected bias-adjustment method for LMMs was not available in the current lmm implementation. Because the LMMs were treated as an exploratory longitudinal extension, the caudal and rostral parts of the cortical regions were analysed independently rather than summed. We also expanded this longitudinal analysis to include several additional whole-brain metrics: the ventricles (as indicators of general central atrophy), the choroid plexus (a marker of altered glymphatic clearance) (He et al., 2023), total cerebral white matter (a marker of general structural connectivity), and white matter hypointensities, which served as a marker of white matter lesion burden (Wei et al., 2019).

XGBoost:

We employed XGBoost, a gradient boosting framework optimised for tabular data, to predict LCMM-derived latent classes from baseline features with the aim of developing a lightweight predictive model. The dataset included PATNO, LCMM class assignment, age, sex, race, baseline clinical scales, DaTScan features, genetics, biofluid markers. The dataset was split into training, validation, and test sets at a 70:15:15 ratio. Hyperparameters were optimised using random search over 100 configurations with 3-fold cross-validation. Sample weights and balanced accuracy were used to address class imbalance. Model performance was evaluated using AUC, and SHAP was used to interpret the XGBoost results.

Limitations, Strengths, and Future Directions

Cohort and Clinical Measurement Constraints:

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these findings. First, while the PPMI dataset provides an unprecedented de novo PD cohort, it represents a highly educated, predominantly white demographic that excludes atypical parkinsonism or early dementia, limiting immediate generalizability to broader clinical populations. Clinically, REM sleep behavior disorder was assessed via the RBDSQ rather than polysomnography, reflecting probable symptom trajectories (pRBD) rather than confirmed diagnoses. Additionally, simplifying the multisystem complexity of PD by representing each clinical domain with a single scale, alongside collecting data post-diagnosis, prevents us from inferring the exact temporal order of early pathological events or α -synuclein propagation.

Statistical Modeling, Missing Data, and Distal Outcomes:

Second, the use of Latent Class Mixed Models (LCMM) inherently assumes discrete categorical subpopulations within a continuous neurodegenerative spectrum. While LCMM natively handles missing longitudinal data, our secondary covariate analysis evaluates baseline variables as class predictors using a bias-adjusted 3-step method (`externVar()`). This framework highlights associations rather than strict causality and is currently restricted to a complete-case subset with overlapping biomarker data. To eliminate missing variable bias and leverage the full $N = 855$ cohort for secondary inference, future work will implement multiple imputation for these baseline biomarkers. Furthermore, while `externVar()` was deployed here exclusively for baseline predictors, it can also be used in future iterations of this work to relate trajectory classes directly to distal clinical outcomes, such as reaching Hoehn & Yahr Stage 3, mild cognitive impairment (MCI), and dementia.

Neuroimaging Feature Selection and Pipeline Consistency:

Third, our structural MRI analysis was restricted to a targeted subset of mostly subcortical regional volumes. This restricted feature selection was a strict statistical necessity: the parameter-heavy, bias-adjusted 3-step method introduces severe convergence issues if overloaded with variables, constraining our initial model and leaving broader cortical alterations unexplored. To resolve this and expand our feature space into cortical thickness and broader regional volumes, future work will integrate a wider array of cortical metrics. To ensure strict within-subject consistency across these expanded longitudinal metrics, future iterations will transition from standard automated segmentation to a dedicated longitudinal pipeline utilizing FastSurfer with Surf-Recon, contingent on sufficient computational resources.

Study Strengths:

Despite these limitations, our longitudinal multidomain approach successfully identifies progression phenotypes based on within-person change rather than static baseline severity alone. The robust associations demonstrating clear alignment between these latent trajectory classes and underlying clinical, biomarker, and MRI features strongly support their physiological relevance to dissecting PD heterogeneity.

K	Log-likelihood	Relative entropy	AIC	BIC	Proportion per class (%)	Average posterior probability	OCC
1	-7504.38	1.00	15016.75	15035.76	100.00		
2	-7403.28	0.80	14820.56	14853.82	27.37 72.63	0.90 0.96	
3	-7326.08	0.76	14672.16	14719.67	19.30 66.43 14.27	0.87 0.92 0.79	27.90 6.11 23.10
4	-7326.08	0.54	14678.16	14739.92	15.32 19.42 65.26 0.00	0.77 0.87 0.68 NaN	

Table 4: RBDSQ LCMM model selection and classification metrics

The 4-class model yielded an empty class (0.00%) and undefined posterior probability (NaN), indicating a degenerate solution.

	A: Class 1	A: Class 2	A: Class 3	Total
C: Class 1	163	2	0	165
C: Class 2	1	564	3	568
C: Class 3	9	2	111	122
Total	173	568	114	855

Table 5: Comparison of class assignments between the z-score multivariate LCMM model (A) and the RBD-only LCMM model (C)

ARI = 0.956; Cramér's V = 0.950.

Figure 2: LMM Predicted Trajectories, for regions where nominal differences were found between Class 2 and Class 3

Figure 3: ROC curves for one-vs-rest on the test set

Baseline Characteristics:

Baseline characteristics across the three classes were compared using the Kruskal–Wallis test for continuous variables. For categorical variables, the chi-square test was used by default; when expected cell frequencies were small (any expected count < 1 , or more than 20% of cells with an expected count < 5), an exact test was applied instead. Specifically, Fisher’s exact test was used for 2×2 tables and a Monte Carlo-based Fisher’s exact test for larger $R \times C$ tables. Pairwise comparisons between classes were performed using Dunn’s test for continuous variables and the same chi-square/exact-test procedure for categorical variables, with Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction applied across the pairwise comparisons within each variable. Continuous variables are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), and categorical variables as number (percentage).

Baseline clinical characteristics showed that the three classes did not differ significantly in age at diagnosis or symptom onset, disease duration, education, Hoehn-Yahr stage, dominant side of symptom onset, motor severity (UPDRS Part III), global cognition (MoCA), or the battery of neuropsychological tests. Class 1 carried the heaviest overall disease burden, with the highest RBDSQ (8.65 ± 1.83), SCOPA-AUT (14.33 ± 7.49), STAI (66.69 ± 18.46), GDS (2.78 ± 2.58), ESS (6.42 ± 3.83), QUIP (0.37 ± 0.80), and MDS-UPDRS Part I (8.28 ± 5.12), all significantly exceeding Class 2 ($p < 0.05$). Olfaction was impaired (UPSIT 20.33 ± 7.76 , $p < 0.001$ vs Class 2), and orthostatic blood pressure drop was elevated (Δ SBP 6.61 ± 13.64 , $p = 0.006$ vs Class 2), however these two features were most severe in Class 3. This group also had the greatest motor and functional impact, with the highest MDS-UPDRS Part II, PIGD score, lowest ADL score, and a marked male predominance (80.9% vs 61.4% in Class 2, $p < 0.0001$). Class 2 represented the low-burden

group, with overall mildest non-motor, motor and functional symptoms, serving as the reference against which the other two groups were defined.

Class 3 occupied an intermediate position overall, with a baseline profile that showed early signs of divergence from Class 2. Compared with Class 2, Class 3 had significantly worse olfactory function (UPSIT 19.85 ± 6.24 , $p < 0.001$), higher autonomic burden (SCOPA-AUT 11.43 ± 6.43 , $p = 0.002$), higher PIGD scores, lower ADL scores, and a greater male predominance (all $p < 0.05$). Although baseline RBDSQ was significantly higher than Class 2 (3.82 vs 2.77), it remained below the diagnostic cutoff. Δ SBP was numerically highest in Class 3 (6.82 ± 15.07) but did not differ significantly from Class 2. Compared with Class 1, Class 3 remained less globally impaired, with significantly lower RBDSQ, SCOPA-AUT, PIGD, and MDS-UPDRS Part I/II scores. Overall, Class 3 was characterized by selective early abnormalities, most notably hyposmia and autonomic dysfunction.

Baseline biomarker and neuroimaging profiles were largely comparable across classes. CSF $A\beta$, total α -synuclein, phosphorylated tau, total tau, serum NfL, and APOE $\epsilon 4$ burden showed no significant differences. Although serum urate differed modestly among classes ($p = 0.034$), with Class 2 showing the lowest levels, this class also had the lowest proportion of male participants, so the difference may partly reflect sex imbalance. Pairwise comparisons between classes were not statistically significant. CSF α -synuclein seed amplification assay (SAA) status differed among classes (overall $p = 0.014$), with Class 2 showing a higher proportion of SAA-negative cases (11.7%) than Classes 1 (5.0%) and 3 (4.6%). Age-/sex-expected lowest putamen ratio was similar across groups, indicating comparable baseline nigrostriatal dopaminergic deficits. MRI revealed several nominal overall differences, including thalamus ($p = 0.005$), putamen ($p = 0.036$), nucleus accumbens ($p = 0.009$), third ventricle ($p = 0.024$), total gray matter ($p = 0.008$), subcortical gray matter ($p = 0.022$), and cortex volume ($p = 0.009$), though pairwise comparisons did not survive FDR correction. Class 2 generally showed numerically larger brain volumes. Cortical thickness measures did not differ significantly across classes.

Detailed values for each variable are provided in the table below.

Variable	N	Class 1 (n=173)	Class 2 (n=568)	Class 3 (n=114)	p overall	Class 1 vs 2	Class 1 vs 3	Class 2 vs 3
Model Indicators								
REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder Screening Questionnaire (RBDSQ)	851	8.65 (1.83)	2.77 (1.81)	3.82 (1.92)	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA)	853	26.47 (2.59)	26.77 (2.40)	26.65 (2.46)	0.498	0.656	0.656	0.656
MDS-UPDRS Part III (includes OFF and untreated scores)	850	22.73 (10.61)	22.26 (9.58)	22.09 (9.55)	0.940	0.930	0.930	0.930
Orthostatic Systolic Blood Pressure Drop (ASBP)	849	6.61 (13.64)	2.98 (11.78)	6.82 (15.07)	0.003	0.006	0.606	0.069
Demographics								
Age at PD Diagnosis (years)	855	65.40 (7.09)	64.95 (7.20)	65.46 (6.49)	0.700	0.831	0.831	0.831
Age at PD Symptom Onset (years)	855	63.94 (7.18)	63.51 (7.15)	64.04 (6.54)	0.719	0.947	0.947	0.847
Years of Education capped at 20	855	15.86 (2.89)	15.95 (2.78)	15.98 (2.84)	0.882	0.825	0.825	0.825
Duration from PD Diagnosis to Enrollment (Years)	855	0.62 (0.46)	0.67 (0.47)	0.63 (0.47)	0.386	0.542	0.934	0.542
Male Sex, n (%)	855	140.00 (80.92)	349.00 (61.44)	85.00 (74.56)	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.256	0.016
Hoehn-Yahr-Stage I (includes OFF and untreated scores), n (%)	854	58.00 (33.50)	203.00 (35.80)	36.00 (31.60)	0.639	0.829	0.829	0.829
Hoehn-Yahr-Stage II (includes OFF and untreated scores), n (%)		115.00 (66.50)	364.00 (64.20)	78.00 (68.40)	---	---	---	---
Normal Cognition (Investigator Diagnosis of Cognitive State), n (%)	622	117.00 (88.60)	382.00 (89.70)	59.00 (92.20)	0.744	0.860	0.860	0.860
Mild Cognitive Impairment (Investigator Diagnosis of Cognitive State), n (%)		15.00 (11.40)	44.00 (10.30)	5.00 (7.80)	---	---	---	---
Non-Motor Scales								
University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT)	834	20.33 (7.76)	22.95 (6.05)	19.85 (6.24)	<0.0001	<0.001	0.709	<0.001
UPSIT Age-/Sex-Adjusted Percentile	834	12.54 (15.75)	17.10 (21.35)	10.10 (12.48)	0.007	0.061	0.433	0.025
Scales for Outcomes in Parkinson's Disease - Autonomic (SCOPA-AUT)	846	14.33 (7.49)	9.44 (5.90)	11.43 (6.43)	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.002	0.002
State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI)	852	66.69 (18.46)	62.69 (17.60)	62.87 (18.66)	0.022	0.023	0.063	0.892
Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS)	852	2.78 (2.58)	2.20 (2.63)	2.15 (2.21)	<0.001	<0.001	0.059	0.469
Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS)	852	6.42 (3.83)	5.40 (3.45)	5.48 (3.30)	0.003	0.002	0.080	0.573
Questionnaire for Impulsive-Compulsive Disorders (QUIP)	852	0.37 (0.80)	0.21 (0.50)	0.29 (0.68)	0.036	0.037	0.334	0.334
MDS-UPDRS Part I	848	8.28 (5.12)	5.69 (4.02)	6.29 (4.04)	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.002	0.102

Values are mean (SD) or n (%). Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$. N = number of participants with available data. Categorical variables: chi-square test; for an exact test, when expected counts were low; for multi-level variables the overall p is shown on the first row. Post-hoc comparisons corrected by Benjamini-Hochberg FDR.

(continued)

Variable	N	Class 1 (n=173)	Class 2 (n=568)	Class 3 (n=114)	p overall	Class 1 vs 2	Class 1 vs 3	Class 2 vs 3
Cognitive Tests								
Clock Drawing Test t-score (age-corrected)	533	64.42 (15.13)	64.74 (13.94)	66.32 (9.81)	0.981	0.977	0.977	0.977
HVLT Immediate/Total Recall t-score	854	45.01 (10.81)	46.27 (11.22)	45.04 (10.75)	0.437	0.604	0.923	0.604
HVLT Delayed Recall t-score	854	44.06 (11.31)	44.59 (12.26)	44.40 (12.32)	0.808	0.831	0.831	0.831
HVLT Retention t-score	854	45.12 (11.96)	45.75 (12.21)	45.49 (12.24)	0.507	0.625	0.625	0.989
Lexical Fluency letter (FAS) t-score (age- and education-corrected)	531	50.32 (10.92)	49.77 (10.95)	49.36 (11.39)	0.857	0.911	0.911	0.911
Symbol Digit Modalities Test t-score (age- and education-corrected)	854	45.20 (9.86)	46.67 (9.65)	45.09 (8.54)	0.382	0.601	0.662	0.601
Benton JLO MOANS Scaled Score (age- and education-corrected)	850	11.74 (2.85)	11.88 (2.91)	12.17 (2.97)	0.318	0.556	0.322	0.322
Letter Number Sequencing Scaled Score (age-corrected)	854	11.47 (2.69)	11.72 (2.86)	11.19 (2.92)	0.176	0.449	0.475	0.257
Boston Naming Test Scaled Score (age- and education-corrected)	507	11.01 (2.59)	11.27 (2.72)	10.72 (2.53)	0.184	0.659	0.659	0.659
Motor & Functional Scales								
Modified Schwab & England Activities of Daily Living Score	855	92.83 (6.63)	94.23 (6.08)	93.03 (5.31)	0.003	0.016	0.631	0.016
PIGD OFF score (includes OFF and untreated scores)	852	0.31 (0.28)	0.25 (0.23)	0.20 (0.18)	0.003	0.035	0.002	0.035
MDS-UPDRS Part II	853	8.04 (5.07)	5.84 (4.23)	6.16 (3.72)	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.010	0.188
MDS-UPDRS Total Score OFF (includes OFF and untreated scores)	842	39.15 (15.90)	33.80 (13.90)	34.54 (13.18)	<0.001	<0.001	0.065	0.370
Side most affected at PD symptom onset: Left, n (%)	848	73.00 (43.20)	246.00 (43.50)	40.00 (35.10)	0.127	0.532	0.115	0.115
Side most affected at PD symptom onset: Right, n (%)		95.00 (56.20)	309.00 (54.70)	69.00 (60.50)	---	---	---	---
Side most affected at PD symptom onset: Symmetric, n (%)		1.00 (0.60)	10.00 (1.80)	5.00 (4.40)	---	---	---	---
DATSCAN								
Lowest putamen SBR (age/sex-expected)	846	0.42 (0.17)	0.44 (0.17)	0.42 (0.16)	0.406	0.539	0.539	0.539

Values are mean (SD) or n (%). Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$. N = number of participants with available data. Categorical variables: chi-square test; or an exact test when expected counts were low; for multi-level variables the overall p is shown on the first row. Lowest putamen SBR (age/sex-expected): From the PPMI curated data cut. Computed as $\text{Miniputamen}_R / (1.4474 - 0.003780 \times \text{age} + 0.21093 \times \text{gender})$, representing the fraction of dopamine transporter binding remaining in the more affected putamen (the side with the lower SBR) relative to the age- and sex-expected level in healthy controls. Pairwise comparisons corrected by Benjamini-Hochberg FDR.

(continued)

Variable	N	Class 1 (n=173)	Class 2 (n=568)	Class 3 (n=114)	p overall	Class 1 vs 2	Class 1 vs 3	Class 2 vs 3
Biomarkers								
APOE ε4 (Number of E4 alleles in APOE genotype)	805	0.26 (0.45)	0.24 (0.46)	0.30 (0.55)	0.655	0.806	0.806	0.806
CSF Amyloid-β (pg/mL)	283	764.98 (289.89)	853.90 (304.39)	798.22 (242.31)	0.172	0.824	0.824	0.824
CSF α-Synuclein (pg/mL)	305	1418.40 (588.44)	1585.86 (707.80)	1402.80 (525.44)	0.084	0.860	0.957	0.860
CSF Phosphorylated-τ (pg/mL)	289	14.49 (5.43)	15.23 (5.40)	14.61 (4.98)	0.515	0.915	0.915	0.915
CSF Total-τ (pg/mL)	305	167.05 (55.34)	175.09 (58.85)	164.22 (56.85)	0.334	0.924	0.924	0.924
Serum Uric Acid (mg/dL)	791	5.39 (1.29)	5.09 (1.24)	5.32 (1.27)	0.034	0.074	0.567	0.301
Serum Neurofilament Light Chain (pg/mL)	299	15.07 (7.59)	14.09 (7.42)	14.27 (6.09)	0.770	0.928	0.928	0.928
CSF Seed Amplification Assay Negative, n (%)	796	8.00 (5.00)	62.00 (11.70)	5.00 (4.60)	0.012	0.046	0.337	0.124
CSF Seed Amplification Assay Positive (LBD-like), n (%)		145.00 (91.20)	458.00 (86.70)	104.00 (95.40)	---	---	---	---
CSF Seed Amplification Assay Inconclusive, n (%)		3.00 (1.90)	3.00 (0.60)	0.00 (0.00)	---	---	---	---
CSF Seed Amplification Assay Positive (MSA-like), n (%)		3.00 (1.90)	5.00 (0.90)	0.00 (0.00)	---	---	---	---
Subcortical Volumes								
Thalamus Volume	474	0.00436 (0.00049)	0.00454 (0.00050)	0.00446 (0.00048)	0.005	0.221	0.488	0.594
Putamen Volume	474	0.00273 (0.00036)	0.00284 (0.00038)	0.00278 (0.00037)	0.036	0.489	0.560	0.560
Caudate Volume	474	0.00210 (0.00029)	0.00213 (0.00030)	0.00208 (0.00033)	0.744	0.876	0.876	0.876
Hippocampus Volume	474	0.00258 (0.00036)	0.00263 (0.00032)	0.00259 (0.00030)	0.163	0.760	0.833	0.760
Amygdala Volume	474	0.00104 (0.00017)	0.00106 (0.00016)	0.00104 (0.00015)	0.291	0.781	0.781	0.781
Pallidum Volume	474	0.00124 (0.00014)	0.00126 (0.00015)	0.00127 (0.00017)	0.226	0.596	0.596	0.596
Nucleus Accumbens Volume	474	0.00029 (0.00008)	0.00031 (0.00008)	0.00027 (0.00007)	0.009	0.491	0.491	0.303
Ventral DC Volume	474	0.00252 (0.00024)	0.00255 (0.00024)	0.00249 (0.00023)	0.138	0.639	0.924	0.639

Values are mean (SD) or n (%). Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$. N = number of participants with available data. Brain volumes normalized by estimated total intracranial volume (eTIV).
 Categorical variables: chi-square test, or an exact test when expected counts were low; for multi-level variables the overall p is shown on the first row.
 Pairwise comparisons corrected by Benjamini-Hochberg FDR.

(continued)

Variable	N	Class 1 (n=173)	Class 2 (n=568)	Class 3 (n=114)	p overall	Class 1 vs 2	Class 1 vs 3	Class 2 vs 3
Ventricular Volumes								
Lateral Ventricle Volume	474	0.00984 (0.00463)	0.00920 (0.00442)	0.00935 (0.00413)	0.221	0.687	0.687	0.687
Inferior Lateral Ventricle Volume	474	0.00038 (0.00029)	0.00033 (0.00019)	0.00036 (0.00026)	0.579	0.965	0.965	0.965
3rd Ventricle Volume	474	0.00108 (0.00036)	0.00097 (0.00036)	0.00102 (0.00032)	0.024	0.470	0.636	0.630
4th Ventricle Volume	474	0.00115 (0.00032)	0.00119 (0.00035)	0.00120 (0.00029)	0.420	0.666	0.666	0.666
Cortical & White Matter Volumes								
Total Gray Matter Volume	474	0.375 (0.037)	0.383 (0.035)	0.373 (0.034)	0.008	0.301	0.928	0.301
Subcortical Gray Matter Volume	474	0.035 (0.003)	0.036 (0.003)	0.035 (0.003)	0.022	0.406	0.532	0.532
Cerebral White Matter Volume	474	0.324 (0.045)	0.324 (0.046)	0.322 (0.053)	0.367	0.768	0.768	0.768
Cortex Volume	474	0.136 (0.015)	0.140 (0.015)	0.135 (0.015)	0.009	0.315	0.906	0.315
Cerebellum Cortex Volume	474	0.034 (0.004)	0.034 (0.003)	0.034 (0.004)	0.751	0.975	0.975	0.975
White Matter Hypointensities Volume	474	0.00246 (0.00441)	0.00259 (0.00598)	0.00274 (0.00542)	0.199	0.772	0.772	0.772
Choroid Plexus Volume	474	0.00050 (0.00015)	0.00049 (0.00014)	0.00050 (0.00014)	0.965	0.960	0.960	0.960
Corpus Callosum Volumes								
Corpus Callosum Anterior	474	0.00059 (0.00011)	0.00060 (0.00009)	0.00059 (0.00012)	0.584	0.939	0.939	0.939
Corpus Callosum Central	474	0.00034 (0.00011)	0.00033 (0.00009)	0.00033 (0.00011)	0.773	0.842	0.842	0.842
Corpus Callosum Mid-Anterior	474	0.00034 (0.00011)	0.00033 (0.00009)	0.00033 (0.00010)	0.700	0.889	0.889	0.889
Corpus Callosum Mid-Posterior	474	0.00034 (0.00009)	0.00035 (0.00009)	0.00035 (0.00011)	0.771	0.983	0.983	0.983
Corpus Callosum Posterior	474	0.00065 (0.00011)	0.00068 (0.00011)	0.00068 (0.00012)	0.143	0.553	0.553	0.667

Values are mean (SD) or n (%). Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$. N = number of participants with available data. Brain volumes normalized by estimated total intracranial volume (eTIV). Pairwise comparisons corrected by Benjamini-Hochberg FDR. (continued)

Variable	N	Class 1 (n=173)	Class 2 (n=568)	Class 3 (n=114)	p overall	Class 1 vs 2	Class 1 vs 3	Class 2 vs 3
Cortical Thickness – Part 1								
Banks of Superior Temporal Sulcus	474	1.02 (0.06)	1.02 (0.06)	1.02 (0.07)	0.914	0.998	0.998	0.998
Caudal Anterior Cingulate	474	1.00 (0.09)	0.98 (0.08)	0.99 (0.10)	0.130	0.749	0.749	0.796
Caudal Middle Frontal	474	1.00 (0.04)	1.01 (0.04)	1.01 (0.04)	0.334	0.722	0.722	0.722
Cuneus	474	0.74 (0.04)	0.74 (0.05)	0.74 (0.05)	0.525	0.801	0.801	0.801
Entorhinal	474	1.44 (0.12)	1.44 (0.12)	1.42 (0.14)	0.832	0.908	0.908	0.908
Fusiform	474	1.15 (0.06)	1.15 (0.06)	1.15 (0.05)	0.978	0.963	0.963	0.963
Inferior Parietal	474	0.98 (0.04)	0.98 (0.03)	0.98 (0.04)	0.598	0.965	0.965	0.965
Inferior Temporal	474	1.19 (0.06)	1.18 (0.06)	1.19 (0.06)	0.550	0.970	0.988	0.970
Isthmus Cingulate	474	0.96 (0.07)	0.96 (0.07)	0.96 (0.07)	0.591	0.728	0.728	0.728
Lateral Occipital	474	0.89 (0.05)	0.89 (0.04)	0.89 (0.04)	0.955	0.927	0.927	0.927
Lateral Orbitofrontal	474	1.12 (0.05)	1.12 (0.05)	1.12 (0.06)	0.574	0.878	0.878	0.878
Lingual	474	0.82 (0.04)	0.81 (0.05)	0.81 (0.05)	0.417	0.889	0.889	0.963
Medial Orbitofrontal	474	1.02 (0.06)	1.02 (0.05)	1.03 (0.06)	0.465	0.990	0.898	0.898
Middle Temporal	474	1.17 (0.05)	1.17 (0.05)	1.16 (0.06)	0.623	0.951	0.951	0.951
Parahippocampal	474	1.12 (0.12)	1.14 (0.11)	1.13 (0.12)	0.429	0.823	0.823	0.823
Paracentral	474	0.94 (0.07)	0.95 (0.06)	0.95 (0.06)	0.874	0.933	0.933	0.933
Pars Opercularis	474	1.05 (0.04)	1.04 (0.04)	1.04 (0.05)	0.222	0.595	0.595	0.781

Values are mean (SD). Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$. N = number of participants with available data. Cortical thickness values were normalized by the mean cortical thickness. Pairwise comparisons corrected by Benjamin-Hochberg FDR. (continued)

Variable	N	Class 1 (n=173)	Class 2 (n=568)	Class 3 (n=114)	p overall	Class 1 vs 2	Class 1 vs 3	Class 2 vs 3
Cortical Thickness – Part 2								
Pars Orbitalis	474	1.11 (0.07)	1.10 (0.07)	1.11 (0.09)	0.902	0.929	0.929	0.929
Pars Triangularis	474	0.99 (0.05)	0.99 (0.04)	0.98 (0.05)	0.414	0.681	0.681	0.681
Pericalcarine	474	0.65 (0.05)	0.65 (0.06)	0.65 (0.06)	0.576	0.978	0.978	0.978
Postcentral	474	0.82 (0.05)	0.82 (0.05)	0.82 (0.05)	0.327	0.730	0.730	0.730
Posterior Cingulate	474	0.99 (0.07)	0.98 (0.06)	0.98 (0.07)	0.682	0.949	0.949	0.949
Precentral	474	0.98 (0.07)	0.98 (0.06)	0.98 (0.06)	0.775	0.860	0.860	0.860
Precuneus	474	0.95 (0.06)	0.96 (0.05)	0.96 (0.05)	0.128	0.684	0.684	0.684
Rostral Anterior Cingulate	474	1.12 (0.09)	1.12 (0.09)	1.12 (0.09)	0.508	0.931	0.931	0.931
Rostral Middle Frontal	474	0.97 (0.04)	0.97 (0.04)	0.97 (0.05)	0.466	0.852	0.814	0.814
Superior Frontal	474	1.07 (0.04)	1.08 (0.04)	1.08 (0.05)	0.478	0.717	0.717	0.717
Superior Parietal	474	0.87 (0.05)	0.87 (0.05)	0.87 (0.04)	0.600	0.760	0.760	0.760
Superior Temporal	474	1.11 (0.05)	1.12 (0.05)	1.11 (0.05)	0.835	0.929	0.929	0.929
Supramarginal	474	1.01 (0.04)	1.01 (0.04)	1.00 (0.05)	0.307	0.901	0.845	0.845
Frontal Pole	474	1.13 (0.13)	1.14 (0.10)	1.14 (0.12)	0.455	0.908	0.908	0.976
Temporal Pole	474	1.54 (0.12)	1.54 (0.12)	1.54 (0.12)	0.855	0.951	0.951	0.951
Transverse Temporal	474	0.91 (0.09)	0.92 (0.09)	0.91 (0.09)	0.289	0.710	0.710	0.710
Insula	474	1.25 (0.08)	1.23 (0.07)	1.23 (0.09)	0.053	0.482	0.482	0.947

Values are mean (SD). Bold p-values indicate $p < 0.05$. N = number of participants with available data. Cortical thickness values were normalized by the mean cortical thickness. Pairwise comparisons corrected by Benjamin-Hochberg FDR.

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